

D1.2

**Quality Assurance and Risk
Management Plan
(QA&RMP)**
Fist release

skillbill

SKILL TO BOOST INNOVATION & PROFESSIONAL
FULFILLMENT IN A SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY

AzzeroCO2

28 / 11 / 2022

Funded by
the European Union

PROJECT INFORMATION

PROGRAMME	Horizon Europe
TOPIC	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-02-02
TYPE OF ACTION	HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
PROJECT NUMBER	101075587
START DAY	1 September 2022
DURATION	36 months

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

TITLE	Quality Assurance and Risk Management Plan (QA&RMP)
WORK PACKAGE	WP1
TASK	T1.2- Quality assurance and risk management
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DATE	28/11/2022

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

PU	Public, fully open	x
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
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Classified S-UE/EU-S	EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444	

DOCUMENT HISTORY

VERSION	DATE	CHANGES	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER
01.00	10/11/2022	First version	AzzeroCO2
01.01	11/11/2022	Comments and suggestions	All Partners
02.00	22/11/2022	Implementation of partners suggestions; Addition of a new risk (n°15); revision of the scores and of some comments.	AzzeroCO2

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ABBREVIATIONS

AB	Advisory Board
CA	Consortium Agreement
CAPA	Corrective Action And Preventive Action
CM	Communication Manager
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identified
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable And Re-Usable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Life Cycle Analysis
OS	Open Science
PM	Project Manager
PMP	Project Management Plan
PO	Project Officer
QA	Quality Assurance
QAP	Quality Assurance Plan
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
TCC	Technical Coordination Committee
VET	Vocational Education And Training
VR¹	Virtual Reality
WP/ WPL	Work Package /Work Package Leaders

¹ Virtual reality (VR) implies a complete immersion experience that shuts out the physical world. Augmented reality (AR) adds digital elements to a live view often by using the camera on a smartphone. In a Mixed Reality (MR) experience, which combines elements of both AR and VR, real-world and digital objects interact. Extended Reality (XR) is an umbrella term that covers all of the various technologies that enhance our senses, whether they're providing additional information about the actual world or creating totally unreal, simulated worlds for us to experience. It includes Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR) and Mixed Reality (MR) technologies. (www.fi.edu/differencebetween-ar-vr-and-mr)

Executive Summary

This deliverable provides the initial version SKILLBILL Quality Assurance and Risk Management Plan (QA&RMP). The document will be updated during the project life, and a final version is foreseen at the end of the project.

The document Quality Assurance and Risk Management Plan (QA&RMP) covers all aspects related to the technical quality of data produced and risk management of the project.

1. Overview

The purpose of this document is to define a consistent set of working procedures, processes and best practice guidelines in order to ensure the achievement of goals and quality standards of the Project outcomes.

This document is a guide for the project coordination, in order to ensure that quality reviews will occur at appropriate points in the project, and as a reference for all project partners, in order to understand their responsibilities and roles, regarding the project deliverables and outcomes.

This document will also serve as a guide to the Partners in order to establish effective cooperation within the consortium and ensure the highest level of project documentation quality.

Its main aims are:

- To describe the quality management of the project (par 2)
- To describe project risk management (par 3)

1.1 Quality Management– General Definition

Quality management ensures that the project consistently functions as desired. It has four main components, applied to SKILLBILL:

- quality planning: to design a process that will be able to meet established goals under operating conditions;
- quality assurance: to prevent mistakes in the production of document or any other kind of project activities;
- quality control: a process by which entities review the quality of the products;
- quality improvement: to systematically improve the overall quality of the products.

Quality management is any systematic process of determining whether a product or service meets specified requirements. Quality establishes and maintains the standards and procedures for developing reliable products, to meet expectations of customers (in this case European Community; advisory Boards and stakeholders) and increase confidence and credibility, while also improving work processes and efficiency.

Quality management applies to all project activities, including deliverables.

Quality is a joint responsibility of all partners during the project lifecycle. The Project Coordinator (PC) and the Technical Coordination Committee (TCC) have the authority for implementing and verifying compliance with all quality evaluation policies and procedures related to the project.

To that end, quality will involve the review and auditing of project work products and activities by the team to verify the compliance with the applicable standards and procedures.

1.2 Risk management– General Definition

Risk management is the process of identifying, assessing and controlling potential problems before they occur so that risk-handling activities may be planned and invoked as needed across the life of the product or project to mitigate adverse impacts on achieving objectives.

One tool that can be used in risk management is the Corrective and Preventive Actions (CAPA) procedure.

Corrective and Preventive Actions (CAPA) are processes designed to improve quality and handle risks as well as other undesirable situations. The CAPA processes should be well defined to support an effective and efficient project management process. The purpose of the corrective and preventive actions is:

- to collect and analyse information,
- to identify and investigate quality problems,
- to take appropriate and effective corrective and/or preventive action to avoid their recurrence.

The steps include:

- identification of the problem;
- evaluation of the risk;
- preparation of a procedure for the investigation;
- analysis of the root cause(s);
- action plan for corrective and/or preventive actions;
- implementation of action;
- follow-up.

In simple terms, corrective action prevents recurrence, while preventive action prevents occurrence. Corrective action is carried out after a nonconformity has already occurred, whereas preventive action is planned with the goal of preventing a nonconformity in its entirety.

According to ISO 9001, the differences between Corrective (also known as risk-based thinking) and Preventive actions are:

- 8.5.2 Corrective Actions: “The organization shall take action to eliminate the causes of nonconformities in order to prevent a recurrence.”
- 8.5.3 Preventive Actions: “The organization shall determine action to eliminate the causes of potential nonconformities in order to prevent their occurrence.”

2. SKILLBILL Quality Management

2.1 Project quality management

2.1.1 Project quality responsibilities

The Project Manager (PM) is a staff member of the Coordinator, as described in the Project Management Plan D1.1. The PM oversees the scientific and technical direction of the project and the project deliverables, manages financial planning and control, and communicates with the Project Officer (PO).

Each WP is coordinated by a WP Leader (WPL), responsible for the implementation of the respective WP in line with the work description. The WPL is responsible for reviewing and evaluating intermediate and final WP outputs in conjunction with other WP partners; for cooperation with other WPLs and the Advisory Board.

The WPLs have the responsibility for the high quality and the respect of the agreed timeline of the respective technical deliverables and other materials related to their WPs.

The full description of the Project Management with the general structure, roles and responsibilities are reported in deliverable D1.1, chapter 6.1

2.1.2 Quality planning: project documents preparation

The following principles shall apply to all document's preparation:

- All documents shall be written using the standard format supplied (D6.1)
- All documents should follow rules set up in D1.1 for making data findable (with particular attention to par 4.3.2 on file naming, 4.3.3 file numbering) and for making data accessible (see par 4.4)
- All Partners shall ensure the maximum level of quality while preparing the documents.
- All the documents shall have the approval of the WPL and the Coordinator
- All documents produced for the dissemination shall have the logo of the EU and of all Partners.

Documents such as Project Deliverables should:

- I. meet the requirements of the whole Consortium, Advisory Board, and finally of EU
- II. be aligned to best practices for Project Management
- III. be suitable for Web publication and for dissemination activities (confidential deliverables excluded)
- IV. be easy to understand and use. More precisely, shall contain all the information needed by other Partners, to allow them to fairly progress in relevant tasks, avoiding, as far as possible, the necessity of requests for integration, clarification, input of missed data, etc.
- V. be compliant with the Project Management Plan (Deliverable D1.1)

The list of deliverables is described in the GA.

2.1.3 *Quality assurance: deliverables approval*

Document deliverable will be prepared by the responsible partner for the activity, then validated in terms of quality, by the WPL and by PM; the following procedure shall be followed:

- The author of the deliverable shall perform the first document check;
- The deliverable is circulated among all Project Partners, whether or not involved in the same activity. The deliverable will be forwarded for comments at least 15 days before the due date of the deliverable;
- Partners shall give their comments to the author before the due date set by the author (at least 15 days). Deliverables not commented by Partners within the due date will be considered “checked and approved”.
- The author reviews the deliverable before handing it over to the PM for final comments and corrections, if any,
- The PM uploads the deliverable on the EU portal².

Any strong disagreements between reviewing Partners and authors will have to be resolved by asking advice and counselling to the Advisory Board, as described in the document “*SKILLBILL_DefinitionAB_v01.00*” shared with the AB members in the paragraph PLANNED EFFORT: “Deliverables: upon request, the AB will read and comment deliverables”.

The approval of all deliverables must comply with the timeframes for deliverables due date scheduled in the Grant Agreement.

2.1.4 *Quality control: deliverable evaluation*

The deliverables shall have a uniform appearance, structure and referencing scheme. It is therefore necessary to use document referencing and the template provided (WP6).

The content of each deliverable is described in the GA; it should cover all the information relevant to the activity from which it results and all the information needed by other Partners for performing their activities.

The reports should meet a set of requirements, based on the following aspects:

- a) Completeness.** Information provided in the deliverable must be reliable, complete and supported by relevant references.
- b) Accuracy and Conciseness.** Information must be presented in an objective form, minimising the room for misinterpretation or personal bias, and focused on the key issues.
- c) Relevance.** Presented information should be relevant for the achievement of the Project goals.

² the Coordinato uploads the deliverables, not the WPL;
https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/deliverables_en.htm

d) Language features. Before elaboration of the final version, the text must be examined carefully to find and correct spelling and grammatical errors. Wherever possible technical terms and jargon should be avoided; if it's not possible, those terms should be explained.

2.1.5 Quality improvement: performance indicators

In order to improve the overall project quality, it is important to collect data and analyse efforts and performance against indicators.

The Excel document provided in Deliverable 1.1 (ANNEX 2: Work Breakdown Structure; tab RESULTS; OBJ; IND) summarises the overall performance indicators with the target value and timeframe set to reach project objectives, as described in the Grant Agreement.

The performance indicators are meant to measure the performance of the consortium against the principles and processes presented in the current QMP.

The PM will be collecting data regularly, closely working with all partners, and will be updating the values of the table at least on a six-month basis, which will allow the consortium to take corrective measures if needed, in a timely manner.

2.1.6 Dissemination and Communication Standard

During the Project and for a period of 1 year after the end of the Project, the dissemination of the Results by one or several partners including publications and presentations, shall be governed by the procedure of Article 17 of the Grant Agreement and its Annex 5 and of Article 8 of the Consortium Agreement.

All documents, especially public ones, shall have a common format; the formats are provided within WP6 and approved by the consortium.

Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate).

When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

Prior notification of any planned publication shall be given to the other partners at least 45 calendar days before the publication. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement by written notice to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 30 calendar days after receipt of the notification. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted.

Any communication and dissemination material must be approved at least by the Communication and Exploitation Manager and the Project Manager.

3. SKILLBILL Risk Management

“A risk is an event or condition that, if it occurs, could have a positive or negative effect on a project’s objectives”³.

A risk is any uncertain event or condition that might affect the project. Not all risks are negative. Some events (like finding an easier way to do an activity) or conditions (like lower prices for certain materials) can be beneficial for the project. When this happens, it is called an opportunity; but it is still handled just like a risk. The risk is computed from the probability of the event becoming an issue and the impact it would have. Various factors should be identified in order to analyse risk.

$$\text{RISK} = \text{PROBABILITY} \times \text{IMPACT}$$

Risk management is not about eliminating risks but about identifying, assessing, responding to, monitoring and controlling, and reporting risks. Developing an effective Risk Management Plan can help prevent small issues from developing into emergencies.

This Risk Management Plan defines how risks associated with the SKILLBILL project will be identified, analysed and managed. It outlines how risk management activities will be performed, recorded and monitored throughout the lifecycle of the project, and provides templates and practices for recording and prioritizing risks by the Project Manager and the whole project team.

3.1 Risk Management Procedure

The Risk Management Plan described in this document deals with calculating the probability of an event and how that event could impact the project’s implementation, in order to foresee and avoid it or finally to mitigate the problems associated with those risks. The required steps are listed below:

1. RISK IDENTIFICATION: description of what could happen

A checklist of potential risks, in order to have a clearer understanding of them and to focus on where those are most concentrated.

2. RISK EVALUATION: Probability and Impact

After all the potential risks have been identified, each risk is evaluated based on the probability of the occurrence and the potential harm associated with it. Risk evaluation is about developing an understanding of which potential risks have the greatest possibility of occurring and can have the greatest negative impact on the project.

³ Raz T, Shenhar AJ, Dvir D (2002) Risk management, project success, and technological uncertainty. R&D Manag 32:101–109

Figure 1: Probability (or Likelihood) and impact

Having criteria to determine high-impact risks can help narrow the focus on a few critical risks that require mitigation and contingency actions. Each risk is evaluated according to the actual status of project progression and knowledge, so the evaluation can effectively change during the time.

- Assign probability: For each risk identified the project team determines if the probability of it actually materializing is High, Medium or Low, as described in the table below:

Probability		
	0	If the probability of an event occurring is zero, then it will be removed from consideration
Low	1	Rare (<5%)
Low	2	Unlikely (5% - 15%)
Medium	3	Moderate (15% - 50%)
High	4	Likely (50% - 90%)
High	5	Almost certain (>90% chance)

Table 1: Probability

- Assign impact. For each risk identified the project team determined the potential Impact as High, Medium or Low, as described in the table below:

Impact		
	0	If the impact of an event is zero, then it will be removed from consideration
Low	1	Insignificant (Risk is mitigated by normal day to day adaptation)
Low	2	Minor (delays up to 10% of schedule, no long-term changes in the project)
Medium	3	Moderate (delays up to 30% of schedule and few additional costs)
High	4	Major (Delays up to 50% of schedule or major changes in the action)
High	5	Catastrophic (action abandoned)

Table 2: Impact

3. **RISK MITIGATION; PREVENTIVE ACTIONS:** how Probability and Impact can be reduced

After the risk has been identified and evaluated, the project team develops a risk mitigation plan, which is a way to reduce the Probability and the Impact of an unexpected event, in various ways:

- *Avoid* – Eliminate the threat or condition or to protect the project objectives from its impact by eliminating the cause
- *Mitigate* – Identify ways to reduce the probability or the impact of the risk
- *Accept* – Nothing will be done
- *Back-up plan* – Define contingency actions to be taken in response to risks
- *Transfer* – Shift the consequence of a risk to a third party together with ownership of the response by making another party responsible for the risk (buy insurance, outsourcing, etc.)

Each of these mitigation techniques can effectively reduce individual risks and of the project’s risk profile. The risk mitigation plan captures the risk mitigation approach for each identified risk event and the actions the project management team will take to reduce or eliminate the risk.

4. **RISK RESPONSE; CORRECTIVE ACTIONS:** how to react to an occurred risk

After the risk evaluation and ranking, those that fall within the Red zones (as described in Table 3) and those whose mitigation approach is ‘*Back-up plan*’ will be monitored in a strict way, including the preparation of a risk response strategy as a series of actions to be performed in case the risk actually happens. These measures are contingency or corrective actions.

Impact	5	5	10	15	20	25
	4	4	8	12	16	20
	3	3	6	9	12	15
	2	2	4	6	8	10
	1	1	2	3	4	5
		1	2	3	4	5
	Probability					

Table 3: Risk ranking

The scores reflect the status of the projects and they can change over time because of the evolution of the project’s implementation and the additional information acquired by the partnership.

5. CONTINUOUS MONITORING of risks and plans

The determination of the risk and the efficacy of the plans, as the project develops, to conclude if a risk element has become an issue and if the management and contingency plans have to be updated. A risk will be considered closed, so monitoring is not required anymore, when it no longer poses a threat.

3.2 Methods for Risk Identification

The initial risk identification involved the project team, appropriate stakeholders, and included an evaluation of environmental factors, organisational culture and the project management plan including the SKILLBILL project scope, schedule, cost, or quality.

Careful attention was given to the project deliverables, assumptions, constraints, cost/effort estimates, resource plan, and other key project documents. The following could be used to assist in the identification of risks associated with SKILLBILL:

- Brainstorming
- Interviewing
- SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats)
- Diagramming

A first list of all the project risks was given in the proposal submission; this was further elaborated to give a first ranking reported in Table 4; the research to identify other potential risks continue throughout the duration of the project and will be reported in the final version of this document.

3.3 Risk Evaluation, Mitigation and Contingency Action

All risks initially identified, were assessed to categorise the range of possible project outcomes.

For the value of Impact and Probability the values are the ones in Table 1 and Table 2.

The final risk evaluation reflects the mitigation strategy in place; where necessary to reduce the level of a risk, an additional mitigation strategy is identified following the approach described in the paragraph 1.2.

Finally, contingency actions were identified for the risks that are in the red zone and for the risks whose mitigation approach is 'Back-up plan'. The contingency actions will be continuously evaluated and updated.

When a risk, foreseen or not, occurs, any person involved in the project shall notify the WPL and the PM; a discussion for the risk evaluation and contingency actions to be put in place shall follow, involving, at least, the person implicated, the WPL and the PM; the responsibility to perform the actions relays on the WP Leader and the Project Manager will closely monitor the activities, deciding the priorities, urgencies and eventual additional efforts.

The risks already identified for SKILLBILL are discussed in this paragraph following the order of the WPs.

Table 4 gives the concise overview of the risks identified in the project proposal, where a level of probability/severity was already given (low/medium/high, that in this document has been converted into scores (as for Table 3: Risk ranking). Additional comments were included and some scores revised in respect to the project proposal. A new risk was identified.

Risk N°	WP	Foreseen in the proposal	Description	Mitigation approach	Probability (1-5)	Impact (1-5)	Evaluation (Pxl)
1	WP1	YES	Poor performance of Partners/Partner not responding to Coordinator and partners' requests. (LOW prob. /MEDIUM imp.)	<p><u>Preventive.</u> The SKILLBILL partners' long experience in implementing EU funded projects as well as their wide collaboration in similar activities lowers the probability of poor performance of a partner and not responsiveness.</p> <p>All the procedures have been described in the Consortium Agreement enabling the coordinator to identify any problem and to take the respective corrective actions.</p>	1	3	3
2	WP1	YES	Engaging experts and stakeholders in the Advisory Board process proves difficult. Due to time constraints and missing motivation, stakeholders and experts do not contribute as needed (MEDIUM prob. /HIGH imp.)	<p><u>Preventive.</u> The Advisory Board will be set up soon in order to engage the relevant stakeholders and experts in the co-creation process. Experts/stakeholders providing substantial contributions will have fees for their involvement (included in the budget proposal).</p> <p>Stakeholders and experts will also be selected based on their activities and engagement in previous projects of partners.</p> <p>Benefits of joining the Advisory Board will derive from the project's results.</p>	3	3	9
3	WP1	YES	Not reaching the KPIs and expected results defined. (LOW prob. / HIGH imp.)	<p><u>Preventive/Corrective.</u> The KPIs and expected results foreseen in the impact section are based on previous similar activities that partners have already organised under EU projects they participated in.</p> <p>The coordinator, together with the WP leaders, will monitor the achievement of the foreseen KPIs and implement timely corrective measures.</p>	2	5	10

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4	WP2	YES	Stakeholders not involved properly (LOW prob./ MEDIUM imp.)	<p><u>Preventive.</u> Potential stakeholders have already been identified; the consortium's network will guarantee that other stakeholders will be involved. Fees are foreseen for them.</p>	1	3	3
5	WP3	YES	Low number of visitors of the Green portal; not enough /interesting material (MEDIUM prob./ MEDIUM imp.)	<p><u>Preventive.</u> There will be robust communication and dissemination efforts that will be rolled out during the initial part of the project, and these will support channel traffic also towards the Green Portal: the green portal will be linked to the project web site.</p> <p>In addition to that, a web manager and a social influencer will guarantee the correct flow of material.</p> <p>Advisory Board and the stakeholder joint initiative (WP2) will help to define which kind of material can be interesting to several different target groups.</p>	3	3	9
6	WP4	YES	Students are not willing to participate in the European Master/ lack of students (MEDIUM prob., HIGH imp.)	<p><u>Prevention/corrective.</u> SKILLBILL implements a wide range of activities in 7 partners' countries and at European level.</p> <p>In WP2 partners will engage the stakeholder to identify the skill gaps and define the academic objectives and the characteristics of hands-on training and activities, to attract and influence students among other stakeholders; to increase the impact of the project's activities, ensuring that the MSc addresses the needs and interests of the market.</p> <p>In WP3 and WP6 the green portal and the web page should increase the interest in RES and in the project activities, making the Master more visible and appealing.</p> <p>Project events will be organised (where possible) within the context of large-scale international events and exhibitions that will ensure wide participation to boost the student applications.</p>	3	5	15

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7	WP4	YES	Enrolment of students at participating institutions is imbalanced (MEDIUM prob./ HIGH imp.)	<u>Corrective.</u> Limit the number of students who can enrol at each institution. If one institution lacks applications to fill all vacancies, establish procedures to transfer students from one institution to another, if possible.	3	5	15
8	WP4	YES	The MSc degree cannot be validated in a participating country (LOW prob./ HIGH imp.)	<u>Preventive.</u> All universities involved have established quality assessment procedures that comply with the European Qualification Framework. Level 7 courses are regularly validated across Europe upon release of a transcript. Each Unis can provide the certificate for their specific course, foreseen as a specialisation,	2	5	10
9	WP4	YES	One or more elective courses are selected by very few students (MEDIUM prob. / HIGH imp.)	<u>Preventive.</u> The number of students admitted to each elective course is limited and admissions are assigned based on objective criteria: personal qualifications, gender-balance, balanced representation of participating countries	3	5	15
15	WP4	NO	Master starts delayed due to administrative problems.	<u>Corrective:</u> Reduce the duration of the MS (e.g. 18 months instead of 24)	4	1	4
10	WP4/ WP5	YES	Lack of local industries to involve in VET and in the Master for the stage (MEDIUM prob. / HIGH imp.)	<u>Preventive/Corrective.</u> The consortium has already contacted some companies (letter of interest); Universities and EREF have their already established network to involve industries; in addition, other stakeholders will be engaged through the WP2	2	5	10
11	WP4/ WP5	YES	The stakeholders do not provide adequate and detailed information that is required for comprehensive Segmentation and training needs analysis, and finally for the design of VET education and training contents (LOW prob./ MED imp.)	<u>Preventive/Corrective.</u> Experts/stakeholders (WP2) providing substantial contributions will have fees for their involvement (included in the budget proposal). Stakeholders and experts will be selected based on their activities and engagement in previous projects of partners. If they do not provide adequate and detailed enough information an ad hoc meeting will be organised.	2	3	6

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12	WP4/ WP5	YES	Incompatibility of different devices and hardware (LOW prob./ MED imp.)	<p><u>Preventive.</u> Preliminary meetings between Unis were held at the beginning of the project in order to have a full list of devices; this will enable them to check the compatibility and to buy the ones really required for the VRX.</p> <p>Since the coordination of the equipment was planned well ahead of the start of the courses (already several specific meetings performed in Nov 2022), the risk is lowered.</p> <p><u>Corrective.</u> If some device is not adequate, a new purchase (or rent) will be done.</p>	2	3	6
13	WP5	YES	Constraints connected with training room size (MEDIUM prob./ MED imp.)	<p><u>Preventive.</u> As for VET training interaction between users is recommendable, small groups of 2-3 people will be trained per session. All UNIS has a room to perform the VR training (if not available, the gym will be used).</p>	2	2	4
14	WP6	YES	Poor dissemination outcomes not replicable or exploited (MEDIUM prob./ HIGH imp.)	<p><u>Preventive.</u> An adequate dissemination strategy will be carried out (WP6), in collaboration with all partners to attract the best stakeholders.</p> <p>Further, the outcomes are designed in light of future replication in different settings/regions/countries. Wide dissemination and promotion of exploitable assets is foreseen from the early stage of the project, including, mobilisation and mutual learning workshops and debates and coordination of working groups.</p>	1	4	4

Table 4: Project risks overview

3.4 Risk Monitoring, Controlling, Reporting, Acting

Partners will track, monitor, control and report the level of risk of each action throughout the project lifecycle, on a regular basis.

Risks are assigned to the Work Package Leader, who reports on the status and effectiveness of each risk response action to the Project Manager and Project Coordinator on a regular basis.

One of the tools to monitor the project progress and related risks is the monthly project update (deliverable D1.1).

If a risk event occurs, the CAPA technique is put into action and the list in Table 4 is reviewed and re-prioritized and the risk management plan reflects all changes to the risk lists including secondary and residual risks. The lessons learned will be captured and recorded in this document as well.

The steps include:

- description of the problem occurred;
- analysis of the root cause(s);
- action plan for corrective actions to eliminate or reduce the problem and consequences;
- implementation of corrective action;
- follow-up and action plan for preventive actions to avoid recurrences.

The project

SKILLBILL's overall objective is to develop a large and strong foundation for the growth and acceleration of renewable energy's deployment, thanks to engaging with stakeholders of the whole chain, diffusing scientific culture and skilling multi-level workers. The basic idea underlying the project is that the knowledge should be diffused at several different levels and should be qualitatively appropriate to train workers, to increase RES awareness and to reach a more social and inclusive Europe. The project aims at creating several pathways to induce target groups to get interested or involved in RES besides their initial level of education and their working position. It's important, along with the creation of instruments for the upskilling and reskilling of workers, technician and designers, to have awareness modules for unspecific public in order to fight against lack of information and bad quality material on RES, gender gap and the phenomenon of functional illiteracy: it is widely documented that lifelong suitable learning process is the fundamental driver to support the development, maintenance and update of skills. Thus, SKILLBILL proposes concrete actions to accelerate the deployment of renewable energy at different levels to analyse and involve all the interested parts in open discussion using adequate language; create several different pathways to increase skills after having mapped knowledge gap and without gender prejudice; develop and implement innovative learning method; and evaluate the work performed.

Coordinator: **AZZERO CO2 SRL (AzzeroCO2)**

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